

Impact of Television Advertisements on Purchase of Consumer Durable Household Appliances in Karur

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Abstract

The study focus on home appliances which are extensively used in Karur the products are air conditioner, washing machine, refrigerators, mixer grinder, televisions. The study evaluates location wise consumer buying behavior towards home appliance products in Ramanathapuram town. This study was carried out by using a questionnaire and the collected data were analyzed by using simple statistical tools like percentage analysis, Chi-square test and weighted average score.

Introduction

Advertisement is a system of information, with the help of which the message regarding a product's utility, use and availability is passed on from the producers to the consumers. Consumers need information on goods and services, so that they can make a choice between various alternatives. To serve this purpose, the services are rendered from agencies, which are known as advertising media. Different types of media are available for the producer to advertise about his products. They are Television, Radio, Print and Cinema. Among these, the television assumes greater importance.

Television advertising is the latest medium of mass communication and it is widely used for advertisement. It is the fastest growing mass media, which has surpassed all other media, as it is most dramatic and absorbing. As a medium of advertising, it offers a combined audio-visual effect directed to a varied group of audience in a relaxed atmosphere of their homes, where they are more respective to the messages conveyed to them through television advertisements. The effectiveness of the television advertisement are not only concerned with the extent of viewer ship, but also on its impact on buying motives of the respondents, besides, the quality of advertisements in the channels and the slots in which it is aired. Obviously, an advertisement creates a tripartite relationship between the producers, consumers and the advertising media.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the major objectives of the study

1. To find the socio-economic characteristics of the sample respondents and their television viewing habits.
2. To study the factors influencing the purchase decision of sample respondents of select household appliances.
3. To examine the socio-economic factors of sample respondents influencing the impact of advertising.
4. To offer suggestions based on the findings of the study.

Review of Literature

1. **Dr Abdul Brose khan (2014)**, the study examines lifestyle characteristics have a great impact on consumer buying behavior clusters and study highlights lifestyle determinants of consumer buying behavior towards home appliances products in Karur. the findings of the study is to found need recognition of high technology cluster & domestic purchase cluster comparing with comfort zone, the methodology of study is based on empirical method, questionnaires is prepared respondents have been pre tested by researchers in Karur. The study concluded with a consumer possess product with maximum possibility of lifestyle identity.
2. **Dr. K. Sreeranganadhan & Lekshmi Bhai P. S., (2012)** study revealed that that most of the durable manufacturers using advertising as one of their marketing strategies. The survival and growth of consumer durables companies in a competitive environment is not viable without the advertising strategies.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is confined to the television viewers in Karur . This study is mainly concerned with the analysis of the impact of television advertising, the consumer preference of television as a media of advertising and the influence of television advertisement in the consumer purchase decision of household appliances namely Air container, Mixie, Grinder, Refrigerator, Television, and Washing Machine.

Methodology

It is an empirical study based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected from the sample respondents by using interview schedule. The secondary data's were collected from the Books, Journals, Newspapers, Government departments and Websites.

A sample of 150 was selected from the universe by following a simple random sampling method. Using the Likert-Type scaling procedure, the responses of the consumers were collected and the impact of advertising was measured.

Tools for Analysis

1. Percentage analysis, 2. Chi-square and 3. Weighted Average score.

Period of the Study

The data collected from April 2018 to July 2018 (Four months)

Limitations of the Study

As the study is purely based on the personal view and opinion of the respondents, the bias and prejudices of respondents may have an adverse impact on reliability of the result. The conclusion of the study cannot be generalized because the trends may differ from one area to another and from time to time.

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses have been framed for the study.

1. The age of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.
2. The gender of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.
3. The education of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.
4. The occupation of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.
5. The marital status of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.
6. The income of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.
7. The employment of the respondents has no association with the level of the impact of advertising.

1. Age of the Sample Respondents and Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the age of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 1 Distribution of Sample Respondents and Level of Impact of Advertising based on their Age

Sl.No.	Age	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Upto 35	11	56	11	78	52
2	Above 35	11	48	13	72	48
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source : Computed data

The table1 clearly indicates that 52percent of respondents belonged to age up to 35 and the remaining 48 percent of the respondents belonged to Above 35category.

Since the calculated value (0.543) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted. It is clear that the association between the age of the respondents and the level of impact is not statistically significant.

2. Gender of the Sample Respondents and the Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the gender of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 2 Distribution of sample respondents and the level of impact of Advertising based on their gender

Sl.No.	Gender	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Male	11	42	10	63	42
2	Female	11	62	14	87	58
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source : Computed data

The table 2 clearly indicates that 42percent respondents belonged to male and the remaining 58 percent of the respondents belonged to female category. Since the calculated value (0.690) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted.

3. Literacy Level of Sample Respondents and the Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the literacy level of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 3 Distribution of Sample Respondents and Level of Impact of Advertising based on their Literacy Level

Sl.No.	Literacy	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Graduation level	9	45	7	61	40.67
2	Beyond graduation level	13	59	17	89	59.33
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source: Computed data

The table 3 clearly indicates that 40.67percent respondents belonged to Graduation level and the remaining 59.33 percent of the respondents belonged to Beyond graduation level category. Since the calculated value (1.608) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted.

4. Occupation of the Sample Respondents and the Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the occupation level of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 4 Distribution of Sample Respondents and Level of Impact of Advertising based on their Occupational Status

Sl.No.	Occupation	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Employed	14	69	13	96	64
2	Un employed	8	35	11	54	36
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source: Computed data

The table 4 clearly indicates that 64percent respondents belonged to Employed and the remaining 36 percent of the respondents belonged to Un Employed category. Since the calculated value (1.257) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted.

5. Marital Status of the Sample Respondents and the Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the marital status of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 5 Distribution of Sample Respondents and Level of Impact of Advertising based on their Marital Status

Sl.No.	Marital Status	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Married	14	58	12	84	56
2	Unmarried	8	46	12	66	44
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source: Computed data

The table 5 clearly indicates that 56percent respondents belonged to Married and the remaining 44 percent of the respondents belonged to Un married category. Since the calculated value (0.874) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted.

6. Income Level of the Sample Respondents and the Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the income level of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 6 Distribution of Sample Respondents and Level of Impact of Advertising based on their Income Level

Sl.No.	Income	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Upto Rs- 25,000	7	46	14	67	44.67
2	Above Rs- 25,000	15	58	10	83	55.33
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source: Computed data

The table 6 clearly indicates that 44.67percent respondents belonged to Up to Rs.25,000 and the remaining 55.33 percent of the respondents belonged to above Rs.25,000 category. Since the calculated value (3.291) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted.

7. Employment of the Spouse of Sample Respondents and the Level of Impact

Null hypothesis: “There is no statistically significant association between the employment status of the spouse of the respondents and the level of impact of advertising”.

Table 7 Distribution of sample respondents and level of impact of advertising based on their employment

Sl.No.	Employment status spouse	Level of Impact			Total	Percentage
		Low	Medium	High		
1	Employed	10	51	15	76	50.67
2	Not employed	12	53	9	74	49.33
	Total	22	104	24	150	100

Source: Computed data

The table 7 clearly indicates that 50.67percent respondents belonged to Employed and the remaining 49.33 percent of the respondents belonged to Not employed category. Since the calculated value (1.694) is less than the table value (5.99), the null hypotheses is accepted.

Findings

The following are the major findings of the study

1. It is disclosed that a majority of the sample respondents (52 per cent) belong to the age group of upto 35 years.
2. It is evident that a majority of the sample respondents (58 per cent) belong to female category.
3. It is found that a majority of the sample respondents are educated above graduate level (59.33 per cent).
4. It is found that advertising majority of sample respondents (64 per cent) are employed.
5. It is found that a majority of the sample respondents (56 per cent) belong to married category.
6. It is ascertained that a majority of sample respondents (55.33 per cent) are in the income level of above Rs 25,000.
7. It is found that a majority of the sample respondents (50.67 per cent) whose spouses are employed.

Suggestions

The researcher has made the following suggestions based on the study:

1. Television has been a powerful media of advertising and hence the producers are suggested to rely more on television advertisements advertising their products and introduce new concepts in the market.
2. Since advertising on television is costly, small producers and retailers may prefer local cable television network for advertising their products and services.
3. The most popularly watched timings by the members of a family is between 8.00 pm and 10.00 pm and this slot may be effectively used so as to influence the decision making on products which help joint decision-making.

Conclusion

Despite the advent of Internet, World Wide Web, e-mail and SMS (Short Message Service) advertising, television remains a powerful, glamorous and most prepared medium of advertising till date. Therefore, a new product launched may be more effective if advertisements are done through television. Though, the present study reveals that the consumers rely only to a moderate extent on the advertisements in television for understanding the features of a product and making the brand choice, still it is ranked as the most influential medium that helps in making purchase decision and consumer durables.

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